

INTERACTIVE VISUALISATION AND ANALYSIS OF GEOSPATIAL DATA WITH JUPYTER

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ABSTRACT

With its open-source policy and accommodation of a wide variety of programming languages, the Jupyter web-application has recently positioned itself as the most popular environment for interactive scientific computing. In this paper, the use of Jupyter notebooks based on IPython for interactive visualisation and analysis of geospatial data is put forward and used as front-end to a back-end platform with petabyte scale storage and processing capabilities. Deferred processing allows computations to be restricted to the zoom level and extent of the area displayed in a map viewer.

Index Terms— deferred processing, Sentinel, Copernicus, visualisation, Docker, Jupyter, IPython

1. INTRODUCTION

Web-based interactive computational environments have recently gained a lot of interest for data analysis in all scientific fields. This can be explained by the ease of use (no software besides a browser needs to be installed) and the possibility to have the server side co-located with data storage and processing capabilities. Among the numerous web-applications for data analysis, Jupyter [3] was chosen for its open-source policy, its wide user-basis in many scientific fields, and its flexibility to serve a range of programming languages. In addition, Jupyter notebooks provide a unique environment for integrating code, documentation, and publication in a single source file, thereby contributing to knowledge sharing and collaborative working.

The developments presented in this paper are implemented on the JRC Earth Observation Data and Processing Platform (JEODPP) [12]. This platform serves the needs of JRC policy support activities requiring big data capabilities for analysing geospatial data. The JEODPP can be viewed as a three layer pyramid with a petabyte scale storage and processing basis. The first layer accommodates massive batch processing. The second layer provides a remote desktop environment with all software needed for further developing legacy applications. Interactive visualisation and analysis is provided by the third layer (tip of the pyramid). The interactivity is enabled by a web-based environment integrated in a Jupyter notebook [3].

Fig. 1: The interactive processing and visualisation model.

2. INTERACTIVE ENVIRONMENT OVERVIEW

An overview of the proposed interactive processing operation mode integrated on the JEODPP is sketched in Fig. 1. The Jupyter notebook provides a programming interface that can accommodate a variety of programming languages. The Python language was selected for its open source and its wide variety of packages for data scientists with processing, analysis, and visualisation capabilities. The Python code developed in the Jupyter notebooks is not directly executing the data processing. Indeed, the processing is merely defined as a deferred execution pattern that is only executed when needed [9]. The code from the Jupyter notebook is translated into a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) describing all processing and analysis logic that is matching the desired image processing chain object as well as the desired data on which it needs to be applied thanks to a selection process based on metadata information. A key element of the Jupyter notebook is the interactive map display. This map relies on the Leaflet JavaScript mapping library, loaded into Jupyter notebook via the IPyleaflet extension. The map contains a selectable base background layer for navigation. The deferred processing is executed when adding a processing chain as a display layer to the interactive map.

The OpenStreetMap defines the default base map for the map viewer. Other base maps such as OpenTopoMap, OpenMapSurfer or the MODIS global composite of any specific

Fig. 2: The main components of the proposed Jupyter-based interactive environment for geospatial data visualisation and analysis [11].

date can be selected. Any given collection of images or vector layers can then be viewed on the top of the base maps while considering a user-defined opacity level. Available collections on the JEODPP platform are based on radar imagery (Sentinel-1), optical imagery (Sentinel-2, Landsat GLCF, MODIS, etc.), Digital Elevation Models (EUDEM, SRTM, etc.), as well as a series of raster layers such as the Global Human Settlement Layer [7] and the Global Water Surface Layer [6]. In addition, a user can easily create a new collection by importing his/her own data. Any raster collection can be combined with arbitrary vector data sets whether predefined or imported by the user. Examples of predefined vector datasets are: administrative boundaries (GAUL, NUTS, etc.), the Military Grid Reference System used for Sentinel-2 tiling, the Sentinel-2 relative orbits, and the European Natura 2000 protected areas.

3. INTERACTIVE ENVIRONMENT COMPONENTS

The core components of the Jupyter-based interactive environment for geospatial data visualisation and analysis are schematised in Fig. 2. The handling of raster and vector data, processing chains, as well as import/export capabilities are presented in the following three subsections.

3.1. Raster data management

The concept of image collection is inspired by the one proposed on the Google Earth Engine platform [1]. More precisely, the JEODPP interactive library provides an ImageCollection class that allows users to search, select, and filter raster datasets based on a variety of criteria. Users can instantiate an ImageCollection from the relevant dataset (e.g., Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1) and then choose a geographic location of interest to filter products that intersect a named location (based on calls to the GeoNames online service). Each metadata in

the collection can then be used to refine the selection by using arithmetic, logical, and alphanumeric operators to get the set of images matching all search criteria. For example, all the images acquired in a specific time interval, which have a reduced cloud coverage and have been acquired by a specific sensor on a given relative or absolute orbit can be selected.

3.2. Vector data management

A section of the interactive library is dedicated to the management of vector datasets. Thanks to the mapnik library [5] that allows vector to raster conversion based on rules, vector data are treated in the same way as raster data. The display of vector data can be easily customised by editing all visual attributes (colours, thicknesses, line and fill types, etc.) as well as constructing display legends based on data attributes (single or graduated colour or legends) with colours selected from a vast palette library or directly specified by the user.

3.3. Data processing chains

From the instance of ImageCollection, the user can generate a processing chain by applying data transformation operators to obtain the required analysis and visualisation result. Available operators include the following categories: pixel based operators (e.g., masking, filtering, and band arithmetic), index calculation (NDVI, NDWI, etc.), RGB combination (on-the-fly visualisation of three different processing chains in RGB mode), merging and blending (combination of two or more processing chains using alpha transparency), morphological operators, segmentation, legend management (using predefined legends or creating custom ones from a user-defined list of colours), etc. The resulting processing chain can then be added as a layer to the map and displayed inside the notebook with the ability to zoom and pan. The processing takes place on the basis of the user's display requests: the displayed tiles are calculated in parallel and only at the zoom level required and on the currently displayed extent to achieve on-the-fly rendering even in the presence of extremely complex calculation chains.

More precisely, when adding a processing chain to a map, this processing chain and associated filtered collection are converted to a JSON string. This string is then saved to a database instance linked with a unique identifier (hash code). At the level of the map view, this launches an event to add map tiles based on URLs encapsulating the tile coordinates, zoom level, and a hash code referring to the JSON string defining the required processing. The service responding to this tile request is handled by a Python-enabled web server cluster. The cluster servers read the hash code, retrieve the processing chain definition from the database, apply all processing steps to the selected image data, and compose the map tile that is returned to the IPyleaflet map client where it is displayed. The concurrent map tile requests are already providing some basic parallel processing since multiple requests are triggered in

parallel. In addition, the data reading and processing is performed in a multi-threaded environment where it is possible to make use of the cluster resources to ensure fast responses for the interactive display.

It is possible to build processing chains that integrate raster and vector in the same computing chain. Operations such as masking, selection, filtering, etc. can be applied to combinations of raster and vector data.

All interactive processing and visualisation are performed in the Google Mercator projection at the current zoom level on 256 by 256 pixel tiles. The available input raster data are stored on disk as flat files as downloaded from the respective data source. If needed, faster access can be obtained by converting them in GeoTIFF format with internal tiling and LZW compression. In any case, each single file is complemented by a pyramid representation using overviews as created by the GDAL library. While the visualisation is always based on the production of 256 by 256 pixel tiles, three different schemes are used during processing depending on the type of operations considered:

1. Pixel based operations allow for the 256 by 256 pixel tiles to be processed in parallel and independently;
2. Neighbourhood based operations are addressed by processing tiles in parallel while enlarging them proportionally to the size of the neighbourhood. The processed tiles are clipped accordingly before delivering them the view map;
3. Connectivity based operations such as those resulting from the watershed segmentation or constrained connectivity [10] are handled by processing the whole viewed area and then subsequently tile the results for the view map.

For efficiency reasons, actual image processing is performed through code written in lower level (compiled) languages (C and C++), but this is transparent to the user of the Python package. Functions written in these lower level languages are made available in Python thanks to the automatic wrapping provided by SWIG (Simple Wrapper Interface Generator). This was done for all the functions originating from the *pktools* software suite [4] for processing geospatial data as well as a series of morphological image analysis functions including hierarchical image segmentation based on constrained connectivity [10].

3.4. Data import/export functions

Of great importance to users are the import and export functions of what is displayed and processed. The JEODPP interactive visualisation component can be used to export any processing chain into a georeferenced TIFF image by selecting extent and output zoom level (with some limitations on the total number of pixels involved and a quota system for

storage). This allows users to easily integrate data discovered, analysed, and pre-processed inside JEODPP with external data management and processing solutions, thus allowing better integration and acceptance of the platform. An export method that produces a numpy array out of any band of a processing chain was added, gaining access to a whole suite of powerful data analysis tools. A more evolved product of the JEODPP platform is the ability to export an animation containing a time series. Consider, for example, high-resolution satellite satellites such as Sentinels 2, which, with the recent launch of the Sentinel 2B, can provide an updated image every 5 days (and even less for areas covered by more than one orbit). With only one call to interactive library functions, users can export an animated GIF containing the time sequence of all images on a given geographic location, providing a product of great visual and analytical impact. Also the opposite can be easily achieved: users can upload raster and vector data, in any standard GIS format and SRS, to the notebook management system and get them visualised on the interactive map and combined on-the-fly with other types of data.

4. NOTEBOOK GALLERY

The interactive visualisation and analysis of geospatial data with Jupyter is illustrated in Fig. 3 with three Jupyter notebook snapshots showing the on-the-fly processing and rendering of the European Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the NATURA 2000 vector layers, and the segmentation of Sentinel-2 imagery.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND OUTLOOK

Jupyter offers a very rich environment for interactive visualisation and analysis of raster and vector data sets. The forthcoming operational (v.1.0) *JupyterLab* [2] with its improved interface and user experience will further contribute to knowledge sharing within and across research and governmental organisations. In parallel, the Earth Observation big data shift is calling for the development of protocols and application programming interfaces with other platforms to facilitate cross-platform interactions. In particular, the deployment of some of the functions of the proposed Jupyter based interface on the future Copernicus Data and Information Services (DIAS) will be investigated. Finally, the proposed interactive visualisation and analysis of geospatial data with Jupyter can be used in combination or applied to other types of data. By distributing predefined notebooks it offers an ideal ecosystem for conveying evidence based information in the context of data for policy. Interaction with the data is even accessible to non-programmers thanks to the use of widgets. Extension to other data and application domains for extracting policy relevant information currently include news event and social media monitoring [8] are expected.

Fig. 3: JEODPP Jupyter notebook gallery with map view over Toulouse. Top: on-the-fly rendering of the European DEM with widgets to control the rendering parameters. Middle: NATURA 2000 vector layer. Bottom: constrained connectivity segmentation of a Sentinel-2 collection on band 4 using a local range set to 256 and a global range set to 1024.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Gorelick, N. et al. “Google Earth Engine: Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone”. *Remote Sensing of Environment* (2017). DOI: 10.1016/j.rse.2017.06.031.
- [2] Granger, B. and Grout, J. “JupyterLab: Building Blocks for Interactive Computing”. Slides presented at SciPy’2016. URL: <http://archive.ipynon.org/media/SciPy2016JupyterLab.pdf>.
- [3] Kluyver, T. et al. “Jupyter Notebooks — A publishing format for reproducible computational workflows”. *Positioning and Power in Academic Publishing: Players, Agents and Agendas* (2016), p. 87. DOI: 10.3233/978-1-61499-649-1-87.
- [4] McInerney, D. and Kempeneers, P. “Pktools”. In: *Open Source Geospatial Tools*. Earth Systems Data and Models. Springer-Verlag, 2014. Chap. 12, pp. 173–197. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-01824-9_12.
- [5] Pavlenko, A. “Open source renders the world”. *Bulletin of the Society of Cartographers* 40.1-2 (2006), pp. 13–16.
- [6] Pekel, J.-F. et al. “High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes”. *Nature* 540.7633 (2016), pp. 418–422. DOI: 10.1038/nature20584.
- [7] Pesaresi, M. et al. “Assessment of the Added-Value of Sentinel-2 for Detecting Built-up Areas”. *Remote Sensing* 8.4 (2016), p. 299. DOI: 10.3390/rs8040299.
- [8] Piskorski, J. et al. “Cluster-Centric Approach to News Event Extraction”. In: *Proceedings of the 2008 Conference on New Trends in Multimedia and Network Information Systems*. IOS Press, 2008, pp. 276–290. DOI: 10.3233/978-1-58603-904-2-276.
- [9] Powell, M. et al. “A Scalable Image Processing Framework for gigapixel Mars and other celestial body images”. In: *2010 IEEE Aerospace Conference*. Mar. 2010, pp. 1–11. DOI: 10.1109/AERO.2010.5446706.
- [10] Soille, P. “Constrained connectivity for hierarchical image partitioning and simplification”. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 30.7 (July 2008), pp. 1132–1145. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2007.70817.
- [11] Soille, P. et al. “A Versatile Data-Intensive Computing Platform for Information Retrieval from Big Geospatial Data”. *Future Generation of Computer Systems* (2017). DOI: 10.1016/j.future.2017.11.007.
- [12] Soille, P. et al. “The JRC Earth Observation Data and Processing Platform”. In: *Proc. of the BiDS’17*. 2017.